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Tribological Characterisation of Bio Lubricant from Cucurbita pepo

L. seed oil

In recent years Bio-lubricants much desired in numerous applications in machineries due to their renewable characteristics, which have high biodegradable nature and produce fewer pollutants compared to mineral-based lubricants. Thus, in this paper, the effect of bio-lubricant (Cucurbita Pepo L. seed oil) on wear and friction characteristics in pin on disc tester is studied and compared with commercially available lubricant SAE20W40. Tests were conducted at different loads of 10 N, 50 N, 100 N, 150 N and 200 N at a constant speed of 3 m/s for 60 minutes to evaluate the behaviour of friction coefficient (COF) and wear at a temperature of 28°C and 100°C. It is observed from the results that, the COF decreases whereas, the wear increases with the rise in temperature and load. Cucurbita pepo L. seed oil (CPO) resulted in a lower wear rate in comparison to commercial SAE20W40. Wear scars on the surface lubricated with SAE20W40 show a rougher surface compared to the pin lubricated with CPO at both lower temperature (28°C) and higher temperature (100°C). This shows that CPO has better lubricity than SAE20W40. The present work indicates that CPO can be a possible substitute to mineral-based lubricant SAE20W40 for higher-temperature workplaces.

Keywords: Cucurbita pepo L, friction, pin-on-disc, wear

1. Introduction

In ancient times people used vegetable oil and animal fat as friction and wear-reducing agents by applying them in between the contact surfaces. With the development of society, people mainly depend on machines for most of the work. To increase the life of the machine the friction and wear must be decreased between the moving surfaces. There are many ways to decrease friction and wear, lubrication is one of them. So, there is a need for continuous deployment of lubricating oil so that the life of machines can be improved.

It was observed by many researchers that friction and wear depend on various conditions such as load [1,2], contact surface roughness [3], sliding speed [4], geometry [5,6], type of material, temperature [7,8], relative humidity [9], lubrication [10, 11], viscosity [11] and vibration [12]. Tribological tests are mostly conducted on pin-on-disc and four-ball testers. For the study of wear and friction characteristics, factors like sliding speed, applied load and temperature are varied. In between those factors, there are primarily two aspects which affect the COF and wear mostly, which are normal load and

sliding speed [4]. Trivedi and Bhatt [11] showed that the viscosity and variation of load play an important role to characterise the behaviour of frictional force and wear.

Petroleum-based lubricants which are used all over the world, after being used are thrown into the environment because of their decrease in lubricating properties [13]. These petroleum-based minerals cause many environmental pollutions like soil and air pollution due to some degree of toxicity and their highly flammable characteristics [14]. Nearly 12 million metric tons of petroleum-based lubricant waste are disposed into the environment every year. The pollution occurred due to this lubricant is harmful to animals, humans and plants. It causes many respiratory illnesses and diseases in living organisms. Therefore, it is necessary to take some steps to reduce the dependence on petroleum-based lubricants and overcome its high consumption [15]. Due to the rapid development of industries, there is a high demand for lubricants, especially bio-lubricants. This demand is motivated by environmental problems that highlight the bad effects of pollution and the need of limiting it [16]. To meet this demand and to make environment-friendly lubricants, many researchers are looking into an alternative to mineral-based lubes. Mineral-based lubricants can be substituted by bio-lubricants, not because of their environment-friendly properties, but also has improved oiling properties such as high lubricity, high viscosity index (VI) and low volatility [17].

In recent times, many studies have been done to study the tribological behaviour of different vegetable-based bio-lubricants and their by-products to develop them into industrial-grade lubricants. Syahrullail et al. [18] studied Jatropha oil, RBD palm olein and palm fatty acid distillate under extreme pressure conditions. They concluded that vegetable oils have potential as a lubricant. Nuraliza et al. [16] found that palm oil has better friction reduction and anti-wear properties compared to SAE20W40. Sing et al. [19] studied the friction and wear behaviour of Moringa oleifera oil-based lubricant at different loads. Their result shows that 5 and 10% blend of moringa oleifera oil offers minimum COF and specific wear rate. Sanjeeb and Rajendrakumar [20] performed a tribological study on coconut, mustard oil and their blend. Analysis of the blended oil was carried out and compared with coconut oil, mustard oil and SAE20W40. They found out that the 50% blend is the best biodegradable alternative to commercially available lubricants. All the studies [16, 18-20] suggest that vegetable oils can be a potential alternative to commercial oils.

Bio-lubricants are mostly extracted from oil seeds. India is a major oilseed producer in the world. About 10 million tons of vegetable oils are produced from oil seeds in India per annum. There are many vegetable oils available in India which are extracted from different types of vegetable and fruit seeds. Due to the high oil yield and easy availability, Pumpkin seed was selected for oil collection for this experiment. Bikash et al. [21] reported that Cucurbita pepo L. seed has an oil content of 48% which is higher compared to many other bio-oils. Choudhury et al. [13] studied the physicochemical, rheological, and tribological properties of Cucurbita pepo L. seed oil (CPO). They observed that the presence of steric acid in CPO improved the anti-wear properties of CPO. CPO contains rich unsaturated fatty acids and vitamin E which has potential pharmaceutical, nutraceutical and cosmeceutical properties. This also plays a role in disease prevention and promotes health [22, 23].

For the past few decades, Al alloy has gained the interest of many researchers who studied its tribological behaviour [24]. The studies were carried out mostly on a pin-on-disk tribotester using Al-Mg-Si as pin material. Aluminium has a low density and it has high environmental corrosion resistance. Pure aluminium Components are relatively soft, durable, lightweight, corrosion free, ductile, and malleable. Baruah and Borah [25]

studied the tribological behaviour of the cast Al-Mg-Si alloy with and without Sn added to the alloy. In the present experimental investigation, the Al-Mg-Si alloy is chosen as pin material. The wear test was done using a pin with flat contact surface against a plane High carbon alloy steel EN31 disc.

There have been many studies done on friction and wear behaviour on vegetable oils, but there is a little investigation done on Cucurbita Pepo L. seed oil (CPO). Most of the research done on pumpkin seed oil is related to nutritional values and medicinal health benefits. The effect of load and temperature on the tribological behaviour of CPO is yet to be clearly understood. Therefore, in this paper, the effect of load and temperature on the friction and wear behaviour for bio-lubricant (Cucurbita Pepo L. seed oil) is studied in a pin-on-disc tester and compared with commercially available lubricant SAE20W40. Tests were conducted at different loads of 10 N, 50 N, 100 N, 150 N and 200 N at a constant speed of 3 m/s for 60 minutes to evaluate the behaviour of coefficient of friction (COF) and wear at a temperature of 28°C and 100°C.

2. Experimental Procedure

A pin-on-disc machine with a data application system was used to collect the friction force and wear behaviour of the aluminium alloy pin lubricated with CPO and SAE20W40. To compare the tribological behaviour of CPO and SAE20W40 the experiment was performed at different normal load conditions with a fixed speed and sliding distance. This paper follows the ASTM G99-95a entitled " Standard Test Method for Wear Testing with a Pin-on-Disk Apparatus".

2.1. Material Preparations

The rotating disc and pin were prepared using different materials. Pin material Al-Mg-Si alloy and disc material is high carbon alloy steel EN31. The composition (wt.%) of the pin specimen is shown in Table 1. A cylindrical-shaped pins with a length of 30 mm and a diameter of 10 mm were prepared as shown in Figure 1. The hardness of the pinned specimen was 81 HV and the Ra roughness of the test surface was 0.45 ± 0.05 μm . Before every test, 1000 grit size (SiC) emery paper was used to polish the contact surfaces of the pin specimen and then cleaned with acetone.

Table 1. Al-Mg-Si alloy material Composition (wt.%) [25]

Elements	Alloy
Mg	0.89
Si	0.35
Fe	0.25
Cu	0.05
Mn	0.12
Al	Balance

Figure 1. (a) Cast Al-Mg-Si alloy (b) Pin specimen.

Figure 2. Schematic diagram of the plain disc with wear track diameter.

The EN31 is a high-carbon steel alloy which has a high tensile and compressive strength with good wear resistance. The diameter of the disc was 80 mm with a thickness of 10 mm as shown in Figure 2.

2.2 Lubricant

Cucurbita Pepo L. (CPL) Seed was purchased from Guwahati, Assam, India. The seeds were cleaned from vegetables and washed off the external materials. The seeds were then sun-dried for seven successive days and ground into fine powders. The Soxhlet extraction method was used to extract the oil from the powdered seed. The powdered seed of CPL was placed inside a thimble of Soxhlet extractor.

Figure 3. (a) Soxhlet extractor and (b) Rotatory vacuum evaporator.

A spherical bottom flask containing N-hexene (40-60°C) as an extractor solvent was placed at the lower end of the Soxhlet. When the solvent remaining in Soxhlet becomes colourless than the N-hexene extract was collected from the flask. The N-hexene extract so obtained was evaporated under low pressure in a rotatory vacuum evaporator (Make: IKA-RV-3V, Germany) to obtain the lubricant. Figure 3(a) shows the Soxhlet extractor and Figure 3(b) the rotatory vacuum evaporator.

The yield of CPL seed is expressed in Eq.1.

$$\left(\text{Yield of CPL seed} = \frac{\text{mass of CPO}}{\text{Mass of the sample}} \right) \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

2.3 Rheological properties

The rheological properties of CPO and SAE20W40 oil samples were measured using Anton Paar's Modula compact Rheometer (MCR-102). A cone-and-plate geometry was used as per the standard ISO 3219. The diameter of the cone and plate geometry was 40 mm and the cone angle is 1°. Each measurement was performed using a sample volume of less than 1 ml. The increase and decrease in temperature was controlled by using a flange ring, which uses the Peltier effect. The viscosity was measured at temperatures of 40°C and 100°C with a shear rate of 100-1000 s⁻¹. Viscosity index (VI) is calculated using Eq.2 [13].

$$VI = \left\{ \frac{[(\text{antilog}N) - 1]}{0.00715} \right\} + 100 \quad (2)$$

Where $N = \left(\frac{\log H - \log U}{\log Y} \right)$

U and Y are kinematic viscosity (mm²/s) of considered oil (CPO and SAE20W40) at 40°C and 100°C respectively. H is kinematic viscosity (mm²/s) at 40°C of oil at 100 VI.

Figure 4. (a) Cucurbita pepo L. seed oil (CPO) and (b) SAE20W40 Engine oil.

Table 2. Rheological Properties of CPO and SAE 20W40

Oil Type	Kinematic Viscosity (mm ² /s) at 40°C	Kinematic Viscosity (mm ² /s) at 100°C	Viscosity Index
Cucurbita pepo L. seed oil (CPO)	54.17	11.36	180
SAE 20W40	121.88	14.2	116

Figure 4(a) shows the bio-lubricant which was extracted from Cucurbita pepo L. seed and Figure 4(b) shows the mineral-based commercial oil SAE20W40. The yield of the bio-lubricant Cucurbita pepo L. seed oil (CPO) was found to be 13.5% which is similar to the yield of 12% reported by Habib et al. [26].

The rheological properties of the investigated oils are listed in Table 2. The viscosity of CPO was found as 54.17 mm²/s at 40°C and 11.36 mm²/s at 100°C whereas, the viscosity of SAE20W40 was found as 121.88 mm²/s at 40°C and 14.2 mm²/s at 100°C. It is observed that the viscosity of CPO is comparable with commercial SAE20W40 lubricants at 100°C. However, the viscosity of CPO is observed lower than the viscosity of SAE20W40 at 40°C. From Table 2 it is clear that there is a slight variation in viscosity of CPO at higher temperatures compared to that of commercially available oil SAE20W40. If the viscosity of the oil lies between 5-10 mm²/s at 100°C, then it can be used in industrial applications [27].

The viscosity index of CPO was found to be 180 whereas, the viscosity index of SAE20W40 was found to be 116 which is significantly less than the bio-lubricant CPO. The viscosity index (VI) of an oil is the ability to resist change in viscosity with change in temperatures. So higher VI means a lesser change in viscosity with an increase in temperature. The higher VI of CPO indicates higher lubricating film stability at a higher temperature compared to the commercial lubricant SAE20W40 [13].

2.4 Wear test setup

The tribological tests were performed on a pin-on-disc tribometer (Make: Ducom and model: CR 20-HTVT) at room temperature ($\sim 28^{\circ}\text{C}$) and humidity of ($\sim 65\%$). Figure 5 shows the wear test setup and Figure 6 shows the schematic diagram of the pin-on-disc machine. Before each test, the pin and disc were cleaned with Acetone to remove any metal fragments and oil from the contact surfaces. The disk was inserted into the holding device carefully and then clamped into the machine with the help of screws. The pin specimen was inserted into the pin holder and adjusted in such a way that it makes proper contact with the disc surface. The contact area between the pin and disc was examined so that it meets proper contact conditions. The lubricant was applied between the contact surfaces of the specimens. Lubrication was done at an interval of 5 minutes and approximately 2 ml of lubricant was used for each test.

Figure 5. Wear test Set-up (a) Front view (b) Top View.

Figure 6. Schematic diagram of Pin-on-disc machine.

Friction force was measured from the controller and wear can be expressed as weight loss in grams. To measure the weight loss of the specimen, the weight of the specimen was taken before and after each experiment with an electronic weighing scale with an accuracy of 0.0001g. The win Ducom software was used to record the data and display the results. In this paper, COF and wear of Al alloy lubricated with CPO were studied with different loads and compared with commercially available petroleum-based oil SAE20W40.

Table 3. Test parameters used in this experiment

Test parameters	
Temperature	28°C and 100°C
Load	10 N, 50 N, 100 N, 150 N, 200 N
Wear track diameter	60 mm
Duration	60 min
Speed	3 m/s
RPM	955
Sliding distance	10800 m

The parameters used in this experiment are shown in Table 3. Wear track diameter of the disc is set to 60 mm. The proper load was given to the system lever which presses down the pin against the disc. The present experiment was done on five different loads of 10 N, 50 N, 100 N, 150 N and 200 N with a constant speed of 3 m/s. The rotational speed of the machine was set to 955 rpm, which makes a sliding distance of 10800 m, on running the test continuously for 60 minutes. The Ducom instrumentation and data acquisition were used to measure friction force and wear.

The worn surface of the sample was examined with an optical microscope. The worn surface was cleaned gently with acetone for the microscopic study. Since the hardness of the EN31 disc was far higher than the Al alloy pin, so the wear volume is very small. So, the wear properties of the disc were not studied.

3. Result and Discussion

3.1 Friction Behaviour

To evaluate the friction behaviour of the sliding pair a series of experiments were conducted using a pin-on-disc machine by applying the lubricants (CPO & SAE20W40) in between contact surfaces for a sliding distance of 10800 m. Friction data generated from the pin-on-disc controller system were recorded by Win Ducom software.

Figure 7 shows the variation of COF with respect to time for 10 N load at room temperature (28°C) and higher temperature (100°C). It is seen that during the initial 600 s (approximately) there is a significant variation of COF but after that it becomes steady. This is because at the initial condition the roughness of the sliding pair generates additional frictional force. At the same time in the initial run, the lubricating film can't be developed sufficiently thus breaking up the deposited layer and a clean metallic surface comes in contact which increases the bonding force between the contacting surfaces. After a certain duration of rubbing the friction surface becomes smooth and a constant

fluid film is produced which reduces the variation of the coefficient of friction [11] and the COF become steady. A sudden drop in COF after every five minutes is observed for both the lubricants at different temperatures. This is because when the lubricating oil was given to the disc it formed a fresh lubricating layer thus reducing the COF instantly. The COF of CPO is observed to be higher compared to SAE20W40 for 10 N load at 28°C and 100°C. This is because the viscosity of CPO is less than SAE20W40 which increases the chance of direct metal-to-metal contact [16].

Figure 7. Variation of coefficient of friction with time for 10 N load at 28°C and 100°C.

Figure 8. Variation of coefficient of friction with time for 150 N load at 28°C and 100°C.

Figure 8 shows the variation of COF with time for load 150 N at room temperature (28°C) and higher temperature (100°C). The variation of COF for 150 N load shows a similar trend as shown by the COF curve of 10 N load in Figure 7. The COF varies significantly for an initial 400 s (approximately) and with further increase in time the COF became steady. The COF of CPO is lower compared to the COF of SAE20W40 for 150 N load at 28°C and 100°C. This is because CPO with a high percentage of unsaturated fatty acids produces a stable film compared to SAE20W40 [32].

Figure 9 shows the variation of mean COF of Al alloy lubricated with CPO and SAE20W40 for 10, 50, 100, 150 and 200 N at room temperature (28°C) and higher temperature (100°C). It is observed that in the case of CPO at 28°C, the coefficient of friction (COF) decreases with an increase in normal load from 10 N to 200 N. These results strongly suggest that the COF is inversely proportional to the applied load. The COF decreases as the load increases because of changes in the shear rate [16] and also because of an increase in surface roughing and wear debris [4]. During friction, the top layer of the pin gets destroyed and forms wear debris. On applying a higher load these wear debris might break into smaller pieces and roll over between the contact surface of the pin and disc specimen thus reducing the instantaneous COF [28]. The maximum and minimum values of the COF in the case of CPO were recorded as 0.11 and 0.07 at 10 N and 200 N loads.

Figure 9. Variations of mean coefficient of friction with the increase in load for different Lubricants.

In the case of SAE20W40 at 28°C, it's observed that the COF initially decreases up to a certain limit of applied load (i.e., from 10 – 100 N) and then it increases. It may be because at lower load (i.e., from 10 – 100 N) COF decreases due to the development of wear debris and roll-over between contact surfaces. As the load increases the wear debris layer keeps increasing until it reaches a critical thickness and breaks. As layer

breaks, metal-to-metal contact occurs and COF increases for higher loads (150 N and 200 N) [29]. The increase in the COF of SAE20W40 engine oil is affected by the increase in the disc temperature, viscous damping on the friction surface, and greater adhesion caused by the micro welding or distortion or toughening of the material [4]. The lowest and highest values of the COF in the case of SAE20W40 were recorded as 0.09 and 0.13 at 10 N and 150 N loads.

It is observed that SAE20W40 produced the lowest value of COF compared to CPO for lower loads (10N, 50N and 100N) at 28°C. This is because when a lubricant (CPO) has lower viscosity it produces a thin lubricating film, which increases the possibility of direct surface contact between the moving parts and increases the friction force [16]. Whereas, the SAE20W40 produced the highest value of COF compared to CPO for higher loads (150 N and 200 N). This may be because SAE20W40 having a lower viscosity index may not be able to form a stable lubricating layer at a higher load which increases the chances of metal-to-metal contact which increases the adhesion strength and results in the increase in COF [13,30].

In the case of CPO at 100°C, it is observed that the value of the COF remains similar for different loads. It may be because there is not a sufficient change in the viscosity of the lubricant for different loads at 100°C due to its higher viscosity index. The maximum and minimum values of the COF in the case of CPO were recorded as 0.075 for both 50 N and 150 N load and 0.05 for both 10 N and 100 N load, respectively.

It is observed for SAE20W40 at 100°C, COF initially increases from 0.01 to 0.18 when the load increases from 10 N to 50N. Further increasing the load, the COF minorly decreases to 0.13 up to the load to 200 N. This may be because at a lower load (10 N) a good wear debris layer formed between the contact surfaces of specimens, resulting in a lower value of COF [16]. But as the load increases the wear debris layer keeps increasing and reaches a critical thickness and breaks at 50 N load. As layer the breaks, which leads to frictional heat generation, increase in disc temperature, damped surface and adhesion may result in a higher COF for SAE20W40 [4]. Thermal softening of the material occurs because of increased heat, which leads to the formation of the tribo-oxide layer. So, on further increase in load (100 N to 200 N) the COF decreases due to the formation tribo-oxide layer [31]. The maximum and minimum values of COF in the case of SAE20W40 were recorded as 0.18 and 0.01 at 50 N and 10 N loads, respectively.

It is observed that at a higher load, CPO with a higher viscosity index has a lower value of COF compared to SAE20W40 at 100°C. This is because CPO with higher VI produces a thicker lubricating layer at high temperature compared to SAE20W40. Additionally, CPO has a high percentage of unsaturated fatty acids, which indicated a stable lubricating film formation [32]. This indicates that CPO compared to the commercial-based lubricant SAE20W40 have higher lubricating film stability at higher temperature.

From Figure 9, it is observed that for CPO, the COF decreased with an increase in temperature. This may be due to the development of a compact wear debris layer on contact surfaces [29]. Pearson et al. [33] also suggested that the COF decreases with a temperature rise may be because of the way that the oxide particles are sintered to form a protective wear debris bed. Whereas in the case of SAE20W40, it is observed that the average COF increased with an increase in temperature. It may be because of the thermal softening of the pin specimen and increased adhesion [29]. SAE20W40 has a low viscosity index due to which the viscosity decreases with an increase in temperature and the lubricating layer becomes thinner which increases the chances of metal-to-metal contact thus increasing the COF [13].

3.2 Wear Behaviour

To study the wear behaviour, weight loss of the pin is considered by measuring the weight (g) of the pin before and after the experiment with the help of an electronic weighing scale with an accuracy of 0.0001g. Figure 10 shows the comparison of weight loss of pins lubricated with CPO and SAE 20W40 at a temperature of 28°C and 100°C under various loading conditions. When tested at room temperature (28°C) and loads (10 N, 50 N and 100 N), no significant difference in the wear resistance is observed when lubricated with CPO and SAE20W40. However, at higher loads (150 N and 200 N) a significant difference in the wear resistance is observed when lubricated with CPO and SAE20W40. At higher loads, the wear resistance is observed to improve when lubricated with CPO. Similarly, at high temperature (100°C) also CPO showed improved wear resistance when tested under 50 N to 200 N loads. At all conditions, it is seen that the wear rate increases with the increase in loads. This is because the increase in load increases the frictional heat generated at the surface of the pin, resulting in plastic deformation and thermal softening [29]. Hence the strength of the material decreases and the wear rate increases [4].

Figure 10. Increment in weight loss with an increase in loads for different lubricants.

Considering the effect of temperature on wear rate, it is seen that the wear rate increases with a temperature rise. This is because of increased adhesion of contact surfaces and thermal softening of the pin [29]. Moreover, the viscosity index of CPO is observed to be higher than SAE20W40, resulting in higher stability of CPO tribo films at a higher temperature [13]. Hence, at a higher temperature, a significant improvement in wear resistance is observed when lubricated with CPO than SAE20W40.

3.3 Examination of the worn Surface

The microscopic images of worn surfaces for pin lubricated with CPO and SAE20W40 are shown in Figures 11-14 at various loads and temperatures. It can be observed from the microscopic image in Figures 11-14 that a lot of parallel, continuous and deep plunging groups exist on the wear surface of the pinned specimen. From Figure 11 and Figure 12 it is clear that the surface of the specimen becomes smoother as the load increases (from 10 N to 200 N) for the pin lubricated with CPO and SAE20W40 at 28°C. This is because increased applied force forms wear debris layer and breaks debris into smaller pieces. These smaller pieces make the contact surfaces of pin and disc smooth by rolling over between them [28].

From Figure 13 and Figure 14 it is observed that there is no significant effect of load on surface roughness of pin lubricated with CPO in comparison to SAE20W40 at 100°C. Some cracks and removal of materials from the contact surface of the pin specimen are observed when lubricated with CPO for loads 10 N and 50N at 100°C. In the case of SAE20W40, the surface roughness of the pin remains almost similar for a lower applied load (10 N, 50 N and 100 N), but as the load increases (150 N and 200 N) the surface becomes rough.

Figure 11. Optical microscopic images of worn surfaces of pin Lubricated with CPO at different loads at 28°C.

Figure 12. Optical microscopic images of worn surfaces of pin Lubricated with SAE20W40 at different loads at 28°C.

Figure 13. Optical microscopic images of worn surfaces of pin Lubricated with CPO at different loads at 100°C.

Figure 14. Optical microscopic images of worn surfaces of pin Lubricated with SAE20W40 at different loads at 100°C.

This is because as the load increases, the adhesion force increases and micro-welding occurs which results in a rough surface [4]. It is observed that, the wear scars in surface lubricated with CPO show a smoother surface compared to the pin lubricated with SAE20W40 at both temperatures of 28°C and 100°C. The greater the wear scars the worse the lubricity [16]. This indicates that CPO has better lubricity compared to mineral-based SAE20W40.

4. Conclusions

The effect of load and temperature on the friction and wear behaviour for bio-lubricant (Cucurbita Pepo L. seed oil) is studied in a pin-on-disc tester and compared with commercially available lubricant SAE20W40. The conclusions drawn are as follows: -

- (1) The applied load and temperature influence the tribological properties (friction and wear).
- (2) COF decreases as the normal load increases.
- (3) With the increase in temperature, the COF decreases.
- (4) The wear rate increases with the increase in loads and temperature.
- (5) The wear rate is less for pin lubricated with CPO compared to SAE20W40.
- (6) The wear scars in the surface lubricated with CPO show a smoother surface compared to the pin lubricated with SAE20W40 at both temperatures of 28°C and 100°C. This shows that CPO has better lubricity than SAE20W40.

- (7) The present work thus indicates that CPO can be a possible substitute to mineral-based lubricant SAE20W40 for higher-temperature workplaces.

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Declaration of interest statement

The authors report there are no competing interests to declare.

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